

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FORCED MIGRATION FROM UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the problem of the forced migration of the population of Ukraine, the active phase of which in the recent history of the country covers the period 2014-2024. A feature of this phenomenon in the life of Ukrainian society was the wave outflow of the population from the Eastern and Central regions of the country under the pressure of threats to life and security during the counter-terrorist operation (2014) and as a result of the fighting during the Russian-Ukrainian war which began in February 2022. The relevance of the issue is also added by the existing contradiction between the parties to the "emigrant process" to the EU from Ukraine in their views on the further fate of certain groups of migrants (men of draft age) whose rights are protected by the European law, and the lack of a strategy in the Ukrainian government for the return of migrants to the country.

Keywords: forced: migration, Russian-Ukrainian war, internally displaced persons, refugees, "evaders".

Problem statement. In the modern sense the term "migration" is the right of any person to change their temporary or permanent place of residence. Free choice is correlated with mobility and the search for new life guidelines for a free individual as required by democracy. The forced migration is a special type of migration. It involves the relocation of people (both within the state and beyond its borders) under the pressure of circumstances of an internal or external nature and for various reasons. Their objectification creates uncontrollable circumstances that pose challenges and threats to human security and life, and require immediate decisions to change the environment and locality or country of residence. Modern political and legal practice recognizes three phenomena of migrants.

Refugees are persons living outside their country and are unable and/or unwilling to return due to risks of persecution and/or for their lives.

Asylum seekers are people who have filed an official request for political asylum in a particular country. If this request was granted, then in fact they are the same refugees.

Internally displaced persons (IDPs) or displaced persons are individuals or groups of individuals who in order to avoid the consequences of armed conflict, situations of widespread violence, human rights violations or natural or man-made disasters, have been forced or obliged to flee or leave their homes, or places of habitual residence.

A feature of forced migration is that, in addition to the above-mentioned characteristics, this process is greatly influenced by managerial miscalculations and

the indifference of the authorities of many countries to security conditions in general and socio-economic aspects of people's lives in particular [1, p. 64-66].

The purpose of the article is to reveal the policy of the Ukrainian state and the European Union countries regarding forced migration of the population in times of crises in the modern history of Ukraine and during the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. Disclosure of the national specifics of the stated topic [Forced migration from Ukraine] is based on the regulatory framework of state authorities of Ukraine, UN reports and analytical structures of domestic and foreign locations, articles by domestic and foreign authors.

A thorough analysis of the current issues is provided by Ukrainian authors. The works of such authors as O. Rovenchak, L. Amdzhadin, O. Malinovska, I. Mironyuk, O. Poznyak, A. Atamanov, A. Haidutsky, T. Bondar, O. Ganyukov, A. Derevko, A. Suprunovsky, N. Lomonosova, Yu. Kabanets, V. Cherednichenko, K. Zatulko, E. Libanova, A. Golovko, etc. deserve attention.

Among western researchers, the works of D. Zukhovskiy, S. Castles, I. Stalker, R. Hunter and others should be noted.

One of the author's successful attempts to look at this problem comprehensively is the scientific work (thesis of Doctor of Sciences) O. Ryndzak "Migration Policy in the System of Integration Processes of Ukraine" [2].

Presentation of the main material. In Ukraine the phenomenon of forced migration has its own pre-history, development due to the conflict of interests of the political and economic elite, regional and internal dynamics regarding socio-economic problems, the direction and regionalization of refugees abroad during the war of Russia against Ukraine, the peculiarities of the reaction of the countries of location of Ukrainian refugees concerning the prospects of their stay, etc. The multifacetedness and complexity of the specified topic dictated the need to reflect the specified problems by revealing a number of issues inherent in modern Ukrainian society (starting from the 21st century) regarding forced migration. Starting from 2014, this issue has revealed both the commonality of actions of the European community within the framework of EU policy, and the own vision of this issue by the national governments of European countries which runs counter to its vision by the government of Ukraine.

Thus, the article draws attention to such issues as: 1) the prehistory of forced migration; 2) countries of residence and problems of emigrants from Ukraine; and 3) Ukrainian strategy for the return of migrants.

1. Background of forced migration.

In the modern history of Ukraine (starting from the 20th century) within its national borders the phenomenon of resettlement of a large number of people (national-ethnic groups) is primarily associated with the resettlement of Crimean Tatars during the time of I. Stalin in the 1940s and 1950s. This act was based on suspicion of collaborationism of a certain part of the Crimean Tatars with the German occupation administration. Another case is related to the Declaration “On the recognition of repressive acts against peoples subjected to forced resettlement as illegal and criminal and on ensuring their rights” adopted by the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on December 14, 1989 which concerned the restoration of civil rights of Bulgarians, Armenians, Greeks and Germans, who also suffered from suspicion of lack of loyalty to the Soviet government during the war. Therefore, the act of remigration was a kind of step by the authorities towards these national groups regarding their expectations and attitudes.

In the recent history of Ukraine the problem of forced migration returned in 2014, when an anti-terrorist operation was launched in the territory of Luhansk and Donetsk regions. Article 9 of the Law of Ukraine “On Temporary Measures for the Period of the Anti-Terrorist Operation” introduced the concept of “migration” (immigration and emigration)”, and established the procedure for the authorities’ actions regarding categories of migrants [3]. Already in June 2014 more than 18 thousand migrants – IDPs from the areas of the anti-terrorist operation were registered in Ukraine at the level of state statistics [4].

On April 15, 2014 the Acting President of Ukraine, Chairman of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine O. Turchynov signed the Law of Ukraine No. 1207-VII “On Ensuring the Rights and Freedoms of Citizens and the Legal Regime on the Temporarily Occupied Territory of Ukraine” [5]. During this period, many European countries also introduced an urgent abolition of the visa regime for Ukrainians seeking to travel abroad.

Already in early December 2014, summing up the situation with forced migration in Ukraine, UNHCR (the UN Refugee Agency) provided the following figures:

- 490,046 internally displaced persons (IDPs);
- 229,409 people who voluntarily requested asylum in the Russian Federation;
- 7,363 people who requested asylum in other countries [the leading country was Poland – 2,043 applications] [6, p. 1].

In November of the same year, in the Relief Web (UN) report, these figures were even higher:

- 490,046 IDPs;
- 545,613 refugees [7].

In 2015, according to Relief Web, these figures were even higher: the number of IDPs was 1,117,748 people, and the number of migrants from Ukraine was 763,632 people [8]. As the expert community notes the only country within the EU that “truly” got involved in the work of settling the first wave of emigrants from Ukraine was Germany. In October 2015 the country’s government financed the federal project “mobile housing” within the framework of which the focus was on mobile homes for Ukrainian refugees. The project was implemented by direct agreement between the then President of Ukraine P. Poroshenko and the then Chancellor of Germany A. Merkel [9].

However, as the national expert community testifies after 2015 the problem of internally displaced persons remained out of the attention of officials and politicians. In fact, in solving their life problems, they found themselves in a situation of “one on one”. Civil society was silent, and the national media were silent as well [10]. The echo of such inaction of the Ukrainian authorities regarding the social adaptation of internally displaced persons, in particular, and the phenomenon of emigration in the life of the country in general, made itself felt with the beginning of the Russian Federation’s military actions on the territory of Ukraine on February 24, 2022. Its (echo) deep meaning reflected the familiar “natural egocentrism” of a person in extreme conditions, which called for believing only in oneself and in one’s capabilities. In addition, for many migrants it was based on the already acquired experience of life abroad which is an important factor in integration into another cultural and economic space.

Since 2022 the wave of “forced emigration” has gained geometric progression and has captured virtually the entire country. At the beginning of 2023 official data from the Ministry of Reintegration reported 4,867,106 displaced persons but international assessments of the situation already informed about 6-7 million people [11]. This is explained by the fact that not all internally displaced persons were registered through official channels.

The numerical indicators confused two existing factors. The first factor is the permanent situational movement of people, relative to where it gets “hotter”. It is about the “movement of the front” and waves of hostilities. As a result, some IDPs in Ukraine continued and continue to move both within the country and abroad [12]. The second factor is human rights violations. In this regard, forced migration researcher N.

Pavliv-Samoil emphasizes that the engine of forced migration, directly or indirectly was the violation of human rights [13, pp. 70-75]. In Ukraine he claims that the practice of restoring violated citizens' rights is virtually absent [13, p. 75]. According to M. Bil, there is also no consistent policy of social protection of IDPs in Ukraine. The author also closely links migration processes with the social vulnerability of large population groups [14].

The consequence of such a situation in the country was the emergence of a socio-psychological dilemma in society – citizen/refugee, in which everyone chooses the option of behavior and survival in their own way. As unfortunate as it is, but since then the state as an institution and a home of common destiny and residence for a large part of the population has begun to lose its existential significance. The risks of the obvious negative of such a confrontation became even more obvious when the country's leadership and politicians of Ukraine raised such fundamental issues of national stability as the lack of labor and mobilization resources in the country. After all, as statistics have shown, the most numerous group of emigrants is people of working age, with competencies and personal aspirations.

2. Countries of residence and problems of emigrants from Ukraine

According to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine, as of June 21, 2023, 8 million 177 thousand Ukrainians were abroad [15]. In more detail, the picture of the migration flow looks as follows. More than half of Ukrainians are in three countries: Poland – 22 %, Germany – 14.6 % and the USA – 11%. Many Ukrainian citizens have found refuge in the Czech Republic – 7.9 %, Italy – 5 %, Canada – 4.9 %, Spain – 3.4 % and Israel – 2.75 %. Almost 63 % of Ukrainians living abroad are adults, 22 % are children under 18. The age of another 15 % of people is not specified.

Only 1 in 16 Ukrainians abroad is registered with the consular authorities. As of June 21, 2023, there were just over 493,000 such citizens, and 88% of them were adults. This number of people indicates that about 20 % of the current population of Ukraine is currently abroad due to the war as of February 24, 2022 [15].

However, it is difficult to answer what the real picture of migration looks like due to the state of “permanent crossing” of the border which is determined by the dynamics of departures and arrivals to the country. For example, as of May 1, 2023, Ukrainian citizens crossed the border with Poland almost 20 million times [15]. In addition, the picture of dynamics began to be supplemented by the phenomenon of “visiting relatives” who were already abroad by their loved ones and friends. Starting from 2024, it was precisely such “tourist visits” that kept the bar of departures and arrivals to the country at high levels. For example, in the first 4 months of 2024, the State Border Service recorded over 7.8 million border crossings.

Unlike the problems of the wave of refugees from the Middle East and Afghanistan which the EU countries experienced in the early 2000s, Europe received refugees from Ukraine in a more calm and organized manner. National governments, city authorities and volunteer organizations have acted in a coordinated and effective manner as circumstances dictated. In addition,

all this work has been coordinated within the EU and has been supported legislatively, organizationally and financially. European solidarity has played a significant role in this matter. The EU leadership first applied a norm adopted 20 years later which had never been used before. It is about providing “temporary protection” to people fleeing armed conflict. Thanks to this, displaced persons from Ukraine instantly received the opportunity to move freely within the EU, the right to work and small social benefits which guaranteed social support. The cross-border force of this norm has been felt from the borders of Poland, Slovakia, and Hungary to the borders of Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, and Norway.

In addition, the vast majority of Ukrainians has received the status of temporary protection which provides the right to residence, access to medicine, education and the labor market on an equal basis with EU citizens. Some EU countries have also provided additional benefits for Ukrainians (free accommodation in dormitories or separate housing, cash payments, vocational training, etc.) [16].

The consolidation of the efforts of the governments of the EU countries have contributed to the fact that by mid-2024 the primary problems of emigrants from Ukraine were solved, and it itself (the problem) in its “emigration sound” acquired a completely different dimension. It is about the choice of the further life path by the emigrants themselves: either to stay in the country of residence or to return home.

The prospect of staying in the host country for any emigrant means a long path of integration which is not as cloudless as it might seem at first glance. Integration is primarily a change in the usual style and rhythm of life, the basis of which is the restructuring of a person. That is, it is about transforming one's own identity and assimilating the main rules/components of the identity of the host country – culture, history, traditions, beliefs, mythology, narratives, everyday life, etc. The picture of the new reality can be complicated by hostility from the indigenous population, biased attitude of employers, difficulties in finding employment regarding the lack of professional education or lack of competencies, etc. That is, new living conditions can become an unprecedented test for the expectations and self-esteem of an emigrant.

The first bells of the new “realities of life” were felt by emigrants who are in countries with the largest percentage of their presence in the host country. First of all, these countries are trying to reduce their spending on helping Ukrainian refugees [16]. According to estimates by the Kiel Institute for the World Economy, for the period from January 15, 2022 to January 15, 2024, Poland spent approximately 3.3 % of its GDP, the Czech Republic and Bulgaria – 2.1 % each, Slovakia – 1.7 %, Latvia – 1.5 %, and Estonia, Lithuania, Romania and Hungary – approximately 1 % of GDP. For example, in the summer of 2023, the Czech Republic reduced monthly spending on benefits for Ukrainian refugees by a third and adopted a law according to which most refugees are entitled to free accommodation only for the first 150 days after entering the Czech Republic.

The rules for calculating cash benefits for Ukrainians have also changed. For example in Poland, from January 1, 2023 a payment of 50 % of the cost of living in a refugee center was introduced. This applies to those who stay there for more than 120 days. Norway has also followed this path. From now on, Ukrainians who come to Norway (in accordance with the new law) will be forced to live in refugee centers for longer and will have a lower level of payments. They will also be prohibited from returning to Ukraine if they wish to continue their status in Norway. Ireland has set the maximum period of residence in state housing at 90 days for newly arrived Ukrainian refugees. Also, in 2024, the level of social benefits for them was reduced from 220 euros to 38.8 euros per week.

The German path on the arrangement of refugees from Ukraine can be described as a “soft involvement” in a German society. It feels experience in the “Germanization” of the wave of emigration in the early 2000s and the negative reaction of German society to the government’s expenditures from the budget for its maintenance. The new strategy involves the partial cancellation of payments (except for housing and communal) for those who refuse to work without good reason and accelerate the employment process. If earlier Ukrainian refugees had to take language courses to a certain level and then searched for work, priority is now being given to language learning in the working environment. In addition, the qualification and preferences of Ukrainians for work is also considered less priority. From now on, the self-sufficiency of everyone (the emigrant) is a priority in working with refugees through inducing partnerships with state intricate and local business needs

3. Ukrainian strategy for the return of emigrants.

The strategy of the Ukrainian government for the return of emigrants was announced by the Prime Minister of Ukraine D. Shmyhal in early September 2024. As the head of government stated, “The idea of creating the Ministry for the Return of Emigrants is that we pay special attention to the 7.5 million Ukrainians who are currently outside our country”. According to him, this process should be organized, coordinated and has its own strategy [17]. However, the main guideline should be security [personal security] [18]. According to the President of Ukraine V. Zelensky, the issue of the return of most citizens to the territory of Ukraine directly depends on personal security [19].

However, it is obvious that security is not only a fragile increase in the safety of life in Ukrainian cities during the war, it is also the security of the individual in its social, medical, educational, vital, financial and other aspects. In this regard, there are significant differences between the European Union and Ukraine. Their content is determined by the state’s policy on ensuring human rights and freedoms. The issue of men of draft age who emigrated from Ukraine before the war and gained some experience of assimilation into the socio-cultural characteristics of the host country was of considerable importance in this matter.

It is too early to say that the government has a complete understanding of the problem of refugee return. Today, it is more likely that we are talking about

refugees as a factor of pressure on the government’s activities in general. There are also image risks for the country among European partners and fears of losing control over the country’s significant human resources which are desperately needed to restore the country after the end of the war.

According to experts, the government’s intentions in this extremely difficult task are facilitated by three circumstances.

The first is that, according to the latest data, 64 % of migrants from Ukraine have not adapted to life in other countries and intended to return home. According to the survey results, the greatest desire to return to Ukraine is expressed by migrants, who work remotely for Ukrainian businesses – 70 %. Similarly, the greatest desire to return to Ukraine is expressed by migrants, who are temporarily unemployed – 68 % for various reasons: education, profession, language skills, etc.

The second is that the desire to return to Ukraine is influenced by the level of aggressive behavior of citizens of host countries towards migrants. At least 23 % of respondents reported that they had a corresponding negative experience [16].

The third is that the choice of the option of returning to the country is facilitated by the change in rhetoric around the immigration problem on the part of European politicians and a part of the population of host countries. Thus, migration experts from the analytical center European Policy Centre Alberto-Horst Neidhardt says that “the rhetoric around the immigration problem is becoming tougher throughout Europe. In many EU countries there is an emergency situation with refugees. The prospect of further arrivals of people from Ukraine and other regions of the world will increase pressure on the authorities” [20]. The example of Poland is the most alarming signal in this regard. Thus, citing Euractiv, “European Truth” states that the number of Poles who believe that the country should accept Ukrainian refugees has fallen to 53 % which is the lowest figure since February 2022, when 94% of respondents said that they supported accepting refugees [21].

The concerns of Europeans have also been heightened by the circumstances of the “superposition of situations” with emigrants of different waves in time. The point is that in the period 2010-2020 EU countries have already received about 680,000 applications for asylum from citizens of Syria, Afghanistan and some African and Asian countries. This is 54 % more than in the same period of the previous year [20]. Thus, European hospitality is being replaced by fatigue and negativity towards those who arrive “ready for anything”. Today, Europeans are pressured by growing inflation, and state budgets lack funds for social payments to the local population. And this, as is known, is not only a question of social peace in the country. This is a question of the political well-being of local elites, and no political force in power is willing to risk it for the sake of Ukraine’s problems.

In contrast to the intentions of the Ukrainian government to return emigrants, there are also three circumstances that clearly dissonant with the previous indicators. That is, it is about “rejection” of oneself from one’s homeland and everything that is happening there.

The first circumstance is that a third of Ukrainian refugees who currently live in Germany, Poland and the Czech Republic are not at all interested in the events and situation in Ukraine. This is evidenced by the results of a survey by the Kyiv International Institute of Sociology. 34 % of Ukrainians directly indicated that they are not at all interested in information about Ukraine, and 11 % chose the answer option – “difficult to answer”. Such a tone is a signal of the gradual loss of connection with the country by some emigrants and the presence of alternative options for action among respondents [16].

The second is the uncertainty of the country’s future – 35 %. Uncertainty about one’s future and one’s children is a push factor for relocation which has increased significantly over the past six months, when financial assistance from the United States was “paused”.

According to surveys (47 %), the factor of stability and the ability to plan for the future encourages Ukrainian migrants to consider the possibility of moving abroad for permanent residence [22]. The lack of prospects for a peaceful life in Ukraine is one of the three main push factors that will encourage Ukrainians to stay abroad or plan their departure from Ukraine. The number of respondents in the country who expect the war to drag on for years is 37 %. It is significant that among respondents abroad, the share of respondents who believe that the war will stretch for years is 42 % [22].

The third circumstance is the most sensitive and critical in the emigrant environment. This is the return to Ukraine of men of draft age (the so-called “evaders”) and their mobilization into the ranks of the armed forces in accordance with the requirements of martial law in Ukraine.

Here, attention should be paid to the statements of a number of high-ranking officials. According to the Minister of Defense R. Umerov and the head of the parliamentary faction of Ukraine “Servants of the People” D. Arakhamia, this issue should be resolved in a legal and legal manner with the governments of the countries where men of military age are staying on the basis of the law and through the mechanism of deportation [23]. According to the Minister of Justice of Ukraine D. Malyska, this path is too dubious. “Even in more obvious and blatant cases of crimes committed, for example, by top corruption figures”, the minister notes that “it is impossible to ensure extradition even for them. Courts (of European countries) are very cautious about extradition issues, in particular, due to the fact that we are at war” [23]. He is echoed by the executive director of the Ukrainian Helsinki Human Rights Union, O. Pavlichenko. He also believes that there is no mass legal opportunity to return citizens of military age [24].

The conclusion of the discussion can be considered the statement of the Secretary of the National Security and Defense Council O. Danilov which he made in January 2024. In his opinion, “the desire to forcibly return Ukrainian citizens liable for military service from abroad will not work” [25].

The topic of forced extradition of “evaders” was also actively picked up by the Western media. Already in January 2024 the reaction of the governments of the

EU countries to the “male evaders” was almost unanimous:

Austria: officially called the measure “an encroachment on our statehood”;

Estonia: Minister of the Interior Lauri Lainemets stated that the country would not “drive Ukrainian men to the front” [26];

Germany: Minister of Justice Marco Buschmann stated the following: “We will not force people to do military service or conscription against their will... We cannot force people from other countries to do this” [26];

Poland: The head of the parliamentary committee on foreign affairs Pawel Kowal confirmed that there will be no deportation of Ukrainian migrants, although they would like to create conditions for voluntary return [27];

Hungary: Deputy Prime Minister Zsolt Semyon stated the following: “We do not check refugees for suitability for military service. Hungary will not extradite them to Ukraine” [27];

Czech Republic: The Minister of Justice of the Czech Republic Vladimir Rzepka referred to the European Convention which excludes extradition for evasion of military service, desertion or disobedience to a command order [28].

The Center for Economic Strategy offers a look at the conditions for the return of refugees from European countries. According to the Center’s experts, the main factors in the return of Ukrainians home are:

- safety;
- availability of housing to which they can return;
- the opportunity to earn a living;
- comparison of general living conditions at home and in the country of their stay [29].

In the socio-political space of Ukraine, there is another project for the return of refugees. This is the plan “Return of citizens temporarily displaced, in particular abroad and their integration into the socio-economic life of the state” which was developed in July 2022. The leitmotif of its content was the requirement – “adjacent to the EU policy which is implemented to manage the areas of migration, asylum, integration, border” which only in one case refers to some specifics [30, p. 35-36]. Despite the obsolescence of this document (almost two years) it has a number of provisions that should be taken into account in the issue of forced migration and its perception in society. Especially since this project was carried out on a state order where the key problem was related to the forecast of the return to peaceful life of 15 million people at the end of the war [30, p. 35].

The contradiction of this document is the authors’ statement that “it does not require additional funding”, but at the same time two sources of funding are indicated: the state budget and the budget program under the KPKVK 3901000 (the apparatus of the Ministry for the Reintegration of the Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine) [30, p. 35]. As critics of this document point out, such “strange discrepancies in the financing of the project can already be regarded as a loophole for corruption”. According thoughts of experts, corruption as a problem of the return of forced migrants has not yet been mentioned, but it is at least a significant demotivator for the return of refugees to Ukraine [30, p. 35].

Conclusions

The dynamics and features of forced emigration of Ukrainians throughout modern history give grounds to draw several conclusions.

First, the problem of forced emigration from Ukraine should begin with an analysis of the state of the basic vital elements of the organization of the space of human existence in the country. They are clearly formulated in various international and national documents which are based on the UN Millennium Declaration (2000) and require national governments not only to profess “human rights and freedoms”, but also to ensure their fulfillment with certain opportunities and resources. First of all, this concerns the most vulnerable social groups of the population. In peacetime, forced emigration from Ukraine was caused, first of all, by economic factors and the desire of the most mobile part of the population to improve their standard of living. In wartime, by fleeing from war and the threats to life associated with it.

Second, the Ukrainian government’s intentions to return refugees to the country are hindered by the lack of a clear and substantiated strategy as a mobilization path and a component of a “grand strategy” as understood by the British historian Liddell Hart. It [the strategy] must be filled with a certain resource – financial, economic, social, humanitarian, etc. and be subordinated to a single plan. Taking into account national specifics, it must also reflect the forgotten spirit of social justice and the stages of the perspective of life in a democratic state where there are mechanisms of openness and accountability of the government to the people.

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